

BIOLOGICAL AGE AND TEMPO OF AGING IN MASTER ATHLETES

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Abstract

According to adaptation-regulatory theory, the aging carry out to decline of functional resources of body. But, adaptation to aging turn the compensatory mechanisms aimed at increasing the level of vital activity of the body. The purpose of our study was research of biological age and tempo of aging in master athletes. The 36 physical activities persons and 40 sedentary persons were examined. All persons were separate by age groups: 30-39, 40-49, 50-69 and 60-70. The method of biological age and tempo of aging of the body were used. According to our study the significant differences of heart rate showed between physical activities persons and sedentary persons of age group 40-49. For meaning of vital capacity of lungs the reliable differences indicates in age group 60-70, for breath holding tests in group 50-59. The parameter of statistic balance is better in persons with high level of physical activity. Obtained results are indicates of high level of physical performance in physical activity persons comparison sedentary persons. The research is resulted that in all age groups the meaning of biological age are reliable decrease in persons who has high level of physical activity. This fact indicates of slowdown of tempo of aging in physical activity persons. In our previous studies the concept of physical activity promotion in aging was substantiated. According to this concept, in the process of aging, the adaptive-compensatory mechanisms of performance protection get activated. One of these mechanisms is linked with the slowing of tempo of aging and biological age. The presence of a slowdown in the tempo of aging and reduced values of biological age indicates the activation of the process of compensatory adaptation while maintaining physical activity.

Key words: biological age, tempo of aging, master athletes

Introduction

According to adaptation-regulatory theory, the aging carry out to decline of functional resources of body (Kozina et al., 2018; Willie et al., 2024). But, adaptation to aging turn the compensatory mechanisms aimed at increasing the level of vital activity of the body (Frolkis 1994; Sen et al., 2016). Some authors opinion that physical activity is a promotion factors to increasing of functional state and slowdown of tempo of aging (Andrieieva et al., 2019; Pavlova et al., 2014).

According to submission of aging dynamics the peak of physical performance occurs until 25-30 age and then there is a decrease in the values of its property (Poliakov et al., 2020; Von Schnehen et al., 2022). Moreover with increase of involution process of human body the activation of compensation mechanisms with optimization of physical performance observe (Mehdi et al., 2021; Rinsky-Halivni et al., 2022).

In the some research the mechanisms of professional compensation in workers in aging involution were described (Reshetyuk et al., 1993; Korobeynikov et al, 2001). As a result of this research can conclusion that level of professional performance in 20 and 60 years are identical. But general level of physical performance of a person in 60 year more low than in 20 year person. The improvement of high level of professional performance carried out at the mobilization of functional reserves of body. In due of this process the new elements of functional system which responsible for adaptation to performance. It is compensation mechanism related with phenomena of training in old people (Da Boit et al., 2017; Eckstrom et al., 2020; Cabo et al., 2024).

According to our studies, it was found that with short-term and low-intensity physical activity, age-related deficiency disappears. This is tendency observed in dynamics of physical activity (Korobeinikov 2001; Korobeynikov et al., 2013).

But, in spite of this the most scientific work related of physical capacity is ignored the improvement mechanisms in age involution process.

According to conception by Frolkis aging is a process of decline of adaptation possibilities of body related with genetics and phenotypes factors (Frolkis 1993). On based of this conception the adaptive-compensatory theory of age develop and aging were propose (Frolkis 1995, 2012). In this opinion the aging process is genetically programmed and phenotypically determined.

All physiological systems have a potential reserve of functionality associated with inter- and extra structural structures and homeostasis (Sykalo et al., 2024).

The changes of homeostasis in dynamics of age develop determined as homeoresis. According to Frolkis conception homeoresis indicate the Biological Passport of human and determined of Biological Age. Due with body degradation the adaptation-compensatory changes occur. It changes carry out to as phenomena vitauct (vita – life, auct – long extension) (Frolkis

1995, 2012). One of the promotion factors which improvement of performance and viability is physical activity (Poliakov et al., 2022).

The purpose of our study was research of biological age and tempo of aging in master athletes.

Hypothesis: The physical activity is a promotion factors to increasing of functional state and slowdown tempo of aging. In our opinion, older people age at a slower rate than younger. In last time the numbers of Master Athletes are increasing. The Master Athletes movement as social and physical prevention promotes to improvement of quality of life and health of older persons. But the science justification of this process insufficiently reflected in the scientific literature.

Methods

Subjects

30 Masters Athletes (Greco-Roman and Free Style Wrestling) were examined. All of athletes have high level of sport qualification. The athletes were separated by age groups: 30-39, 40-49, 50-5, 60-69, 70-75.

The method of biological age and tempo of aging of the body were used. This method was elaborated by Institute of Gerontology National Academy of Medical Science of Ukraine (Korobeynikov et al., 2013; Poliakov et al., 2011).

For determining of Tempo of Aging (TA) were used a formula:

$$TA = (SBPa/SBPt + DBPa/DBPt + HRRa/HRRt + HRLa/HRLt + VCLt/VCLa + HBIa/HBIa + HBEt/HBEa + SBt/SBa) / n,$$

Were, TC – tempo of aging;

SBP - Systolic Blood Pressure (mm Hg);

DBP Diastolic Blood Pressure (mm Hg);

VCL - Vital Capacity of Lungs (l ml);

HBI - Holding Breath on Inspiration(s);

HBE - Holding Breath on Exhalation (s);

SB - Static Balance (s);

HRR - Heart Rate in rest (min^{-1});

HRL - Heart Rate after load (min^{-1});

a - actual values (personal);

t - table values (statistical);

n - number of values in formula.

Determining of tempo of Biological Age (BA) :

$$BA = TA * Age,$$

Were, BA – Biological Age

In Table 1 the values which include in formula of Tempo of Aging were presented.

Table 1 Values which include in formula of Tempo of Aging

Values	Sex	Age				
		30-39	40-49	50-59	60-69	70 и старше
Systolic Blood Pressure, mm Hg	Males	120	130	130	130	130
	Females	120	130	130	130	130
Diastolic Blood Pressure, mm Hg	Males	70	70	80	80	80
	Females	70	70	80	80	80
Heart Rate in rest , min ⁻¹	Males	70	70	70	70	75
	Females	70	70	70	70	75
Heart Rate after load, min ⁻¹	Males	130	140	150	150	150
	Females	130	140	150	150	150
Holding Breath on Inspiration, s	Males	90	80	60	40	30
	Females	60	40	30	20	20
Holding Breath on Exhalation, s	Males	60	40	30	20	20
	Females	40	20	20	18	18
Vital Capacity of Lungs, l	Males	3,4	3,0	2,9	2,6	2,0
	Females	2,8	2,8	2,0	1,8	1,8
Static Balance, s	Males	60	40	30	20	10
	Females	30	20	18	18	10

According to obtained data the meanings of TA more than 1,1 indicates acceleration tempo of aging, meanings low than 1 reflects of slow tempo of aging, meanings of 1 corresponding with physiological (normal) tempo of aging.

Statistical processing of the obtained results was performed using the "Statistica 12" software. Since the analyzed indicators were non normal distributed, the Wilcoxon rank sum test was used to determine the statistically significant difference between the samples. To present the data distribution, an interquartile range was used, indicating the first quartile (25% percentile) and the third quartile (75%).

All persons agreed to participated in this study and use the research results for scientific purposes, in accordance with the recommendations of the Ethics Committees on biomedical research.

Results

In Table 2 the values of tempo of aging in master athletes with different age groups.

Table 2 Values of tempo of aging in Masters Athletes with different age groups.

Values	Age				
	30-39 (n=4)	40-49 (n=7)	50-59 (n=8)	60-69 (n=7)	70-75 (n=4)
Systolic Blood Pressure, mm Hg	147 138,5; 148,5	166 133,0; 190,0	145 121,0; 160,0	138*** 123,0; 123,0	135 121,0; 151,0
Diastolic Blood Pressure, mm Hg	85 79,0; 77,0	93* 80,0; 120,0	84 79,0; 95,0	85 68,0; 87,0	79 74,5; 95,0
Heart Rate in rest, min ⁻¹	69 56,5; 77,0	71 63,0; 80,0	79 69,0; 82,0	76 68,0; 79,0	66,5 63,5; 70,5
Heart Rate after load, min ⁻¹	98 96,0; 108,0	96 88,0; 120,0	108 88,0; 112,0	100 88,0; 108,0	90 82,0; 102,0
Holding Breath on Inspiration, s	3,4 3,6; 3,2	3,0* 3,0; 2,8	2,9* 2,9; 2,7	2,6* ^{&} 2,6; 2,4	2,0*** ^{&#} 2,2; 2,0
Holding Breath on Exhalation, s	63 42,5; 74,0	52 36,0; 61,0	55 48,0; 67,0	57 45,0; 62,0	76,5 66,5; 80,5
Vital Capacity of Lungs, l	29 19,5; 35,0	30 27,0; 30,0	30 25,0; 32,0	38 31,0; 42,0	37 35,5; 40,5
Static Balance, s	24,5 21,5; 27,5	16* 10,0; 17,0	17* 12,0; 18,0	18* 9,0; 19,0	10* [#] 7,5; 18,0

Legend: * p<0,05, for concerning to group 30-39

According to data results the significant differences observed between age groups 30-39, 40-49 and 60-69 by value Systolic Blood Pressure (SBP) and Diastolic Blood Pressure (DBP). As a seen at Table 2 the meaning of SBP in group 60-69 more low than in groups 30-39, 40-49.

The value of Vital Capacity of Lungs (VCL) observed the significant reduction of absolute meanings with age increasing. Static Balance (SB) more decreasing in all age groups for concerning group 30-39 (Table 2).

Figure 1 Biology Age and Ade in Master Athletes with different age groups

Legend: * $p < 0,05$, for concerning to group 30-39

The meanings of Biological Age (BA) and Age of master athletes presented In Figure 1. As at seen in this Figure there are non linear reduction of BA for concerning Age. This fact indicates of heterochrony process of age involution. Moreover more significant meanings of BA observed in age group 40-49 for comparison different groups.

In Figure 2 presented data Tempo of Aging (TA) in different age groups between Master Athletes. The results of Figure 2 showed with absent of differences by TA between age groups 30-39 and 40-49. The increasing level of TA observed in group 50-59. This fact indicates the acceleration tempo of aging in persons of these groups. The age group 50-59 characterized of low meanings of TA. In groups 60-69 и 70-75 observed decrease in the tempo of aging below 1. This fact indicated the slow tempo of aging revealed in these age groups.

Figure 1 Tempo of Aging in Master Athletes with different age groups

Legend: * $p < 0,05$, for concerning to group 30-39

Discussion

In our previous studies the concept of physical activity promotion in aging was substantiated (Korobešnikov 2001). According to this concept, in the process of aging, the adaptive-compensatory mechanisms of performance protection get activated. One of these mechanisms is linked with the slowing of Tempo of Aging and Biological Age.

The modern understanding of the aging process in ontogenesis is associated with two opinions on the causes of age-related involution. The first groups of theories imply that the aging process is genetically programmed and controlled by a biological program (Davidovic et al., 2010). The second theories point to errors in the functioning of the organism due to the influence of environmental factors (Brys et al., 2007). But both theories do not seem satisfactory.

We adhere to the integral theory proposed by Frolkis (Frolkis 1993, 1995, 2012). The main resolution of this theory is the presentation of gerontogenesis as a part of ontogenesis. This theory also summarized both opinions on the aging process.

As results of our study that in Master Athletes in age groups 30-39 and 40-49 the Tempo of Aging is more quickly than in older age groups. The critical age for Master Athletes is a frontier 40-49 when the increasing of blood pressure observed. Age groups of Master Athletes 60-69 and 70-79 characterized of low Tempo of Aging and decline meanings of Biological Age. This fact

corresponded with activation of vitaut process (life long extension) and preservation of physical activity.

Conclusion

The presence of a slowdown in the tempo of aging and reduced values of biological age indicates the activation of the process of compensatory adaptation while maintaining physical activity

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